

THORIUM : ITS SEPARATION FROM CERITE EARTHS AND ESTIMATION

BY M. VENKATARAMANIAN, T. K. SATYANARAYANAMURTHY AND
BH. S. V. RAGHAVA RAO

Detailed procedures have been described for the separation of thorium from cerite earth mixtures in proportions approximately from 1:1 up to 1:10 using the reagents : trimethylgallic acid, phenoxy-acetic acid, veratric acid, benzoic acid, ammonium benzoate and tannic acid. Thorium in monazite has also been successfully estimated employing these reagents

The separation of thorium from the rare earths, particularly from the cerite earths, is one of the principle problems of thorium chemistry, since on the ease and effectiveness of this separation depends the commercial utilization of the element. Several methods have been suggested, but few have been investigated in any detail (Moeller *et al.*, *Chem. Rev.*, 1948, 42, 63). In the following pages are presented results of systematic investigations on a number of reagents, many of which are now reported for the first time.

EXPERIMENTAL

Each reagent was tried first on a solution of pure thorium, next on made-up mixtures of thorium and cerite earths, and finally on a sample of Travancore monazite.

The thorium solution was obtained by further purification of high grade thorium nitrate as follows. The thorium was twice precipitated with sebacic acid, and then with hydrogen peroxide. The oxide was dissolved in nitric acid, evaporated to dryness on a water-bath and finally dried to a constant weight in an air-oven at 100° to 120°. The thorium content of the sample was variously estimated with sebacic acid (Mitchel and Ward, "Modern Methods in Quantitative Chemical Analysis", 1932, p. 149), oxalic acid (Scott, "Standard Methods of Chemical Analysis", 1937, Vol. I, 5th Ed., p. 946) and potassium iodate in nitric acid (Meyer and Speter, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1910, 34, 306). All procedures yielded results agreeing within 0.2%.

The cerite earth solution was prepared from monazite from which all thorium and the yttrium earths had been very carefully removed. The earth content was estimated by precipitation from an aliquot part with oxalic acid and weighing the ignited residue as oxides. No attempt was made to determine the proportion of the individual members in the group, neither would it serve any purpose in this investigation.

For the estimation of thorium in monazite, a sample from Travancore was digested according to the usual practice with sulphuric acid and taken up in ice-cold water. Oxalic acid in sufficient excess was next added and the oxalate precipitate was dissolved in fuming nitric acid and evaporated to dryness on a water-bath. The residue was taken up in water, made up to a definite volume, and aliquot portions were pipetted

out for each determination. It may be mentioned that attention was focussed not on an accurate analysis of monazite, but on the efficiency of the reagent as a means of separation of thorium from the rare earths.

Trimethylgallic Acid.—Neish (*Chem. News*, 1904, 90, 196) made the observation that gallic acid in alcoholic solution precipitated thorium as a flocculent, slimy mass while holding other cerite earths in solution, but the subject was not further investigated. Some preliminary experiments conducted by us showed that while the precipitation of thorium was incomplete in both alcoholic and aqueous solutions, large amounts of the cerite earths were simultaneously carried down. On the other hand, trimethylgallic acid in neutral or faintly acid medium proved highly satisfactory. Neither ammonium gallate nor ammonium trimethylgallate, however, proved of any value.

The thorium solution was made just neutral to Congo red and diluted to 150 c.c. Solid ammonium chloride (20-25 g.) was then added and the solution heated to boiling. To this was added with constant stirring a slight excess of a boiling 2% solution of the reagent (i. e. about 100 c.c. of the precipitant for every 0.1 g. of the oxide). A gelatinous precipitate resulted which settled down rapidly. After about 15 minutes on a water-bath, the precipitate was filtered hot through Whatman No. 41, washed with a boiling 0.2% (approximately) solution of the reagent to which a few grams of ammonium chloride had also been added, *partially dried*, and ignited to the oxide. When the quantity of the cerite earths is rather large, the precipitate carries small quantities of these and a second precipitation, as described below, is necessary. The washed precipitate was returned to the original beaker, dissolved in the minimum of hot dilute hydrochloric acid, and dilute ammonia was very carefully added till the liquid reacted but faintly acid to Congo red. Precipitation, washing and ignition were repeated. Some representative results are shown in the following table.

TABLE I

ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths R ₂ O ₃ added.	Wt. of ThO ₂ obtained in single pptn.	Double pptn.
0.1180 g.	—	0.1181 g.	—
0.1180	—	0.1178	—
0.2360	—	0.2362	—
0.1180	0.1405 g.	0.1183	0.1181 g.
		0.1184	0.1182
0.1180	0.4580	0.1182 } slightly 0.1180 } coloured	0.1178 0.1182
0.1180	0.5620	0.1185 } slightly 0.1183 } coloured	0.1179 0.1180
0.1180	1.1450	0.1200 } 0.1208 } coloured	0.1180 0.1183
{ Monazite }			
{ 0.0900 }	0.4708	—	0.0900 0.0898

Phenoxyacetic Acid.—Pratt and James (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1911, 33, 1330) recorded that precipitation of thorium by phenoxyacetic acid in neutral solution was almost quantitative, while Smith and James (*ibid.*, 1912, 34, 281) opined that the thorium salt was slightly soluble in water. A more detailed investigation appeared desirable. The following procedure yields good results.

The thorium solution, which should react neutral to Congo red, is diluted to 100 c.c. and heated to boiling. To the boiling solution is added slowly and with constant stirring a slight excess (100 c.c. for every 0.1 g. of ThO_2 will be sufficient) of a hot 2% solution of phenoxyacetic acid. The liquid is now once again brought to boiling, and set aside to cool. The cooled precipitate is filtered through Whatman No. 41 and washed with a cold 0.2% (approx.) solution of phenoxyacetic acid. The washed precipitate is now returned to the original beaker and dissolved in the minimum of hot diluted (1:2) hydrochloric acid. The solution is diluted to about 100 c.c. and very carefully neutralised by dropping dilute ammonia until it is but faintly acid to Congo red. The thorium is reprecipitated, washed and ignited to the oxide. Some results are shown in the following table.

TABLE II

ThO_2 taken.	Cerite earths R_2O_3 added.	ThO_2 obtained.	ThO_2 taken	Cerite earths R_2O_3 added.	ThO_2 obtained.
0.1140 g.	—	0.1143 g.	0.1180 g.	0.5610 g.	0.1183 g.
0.1140	—	0.1140	0.1140	0.5712	0.1144
0.1180	—	0.1178	0.1140	0.5712	0.1146
0.1180	—	0.1181	0.1140	1.1424	0.1143
0.1180	0.1402 g.	0.1181	0.1140	1.1424	0.1145
0.1140	0.2805	0.1138			
0.1140	0.2805	0.1143	{ Monazite }		
0.1140	0.4580	0.1138		0.4708	0.0902 0.0901

Veratric Acid.—This reagent or any of its analogues has not been mentioned in literature. The thorium solution which should be nearly neutral to Congo red, is diluted to 100 c.c., solid ammonium chloride (15-20 g.) added and heated to boiling. To the boiling solution is added, with constant stirring, a saturated boiling solution of veratric acid. The resulting gelatinous precipitate is allowed to settle, filtered through Whatman No. 41 filter, washed with hot dilute veratric acid in 5% ammonium chloride, transferred to the original beaker, dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid, diluted and reprecipitated. After complete washing the precipitate is ignited and weighed as oxide. Representative results are shown in Table III.

Benzoic Acid.—Benzoic acid was suggested by both Kolb and Ahrlé (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1905, 18, 92) and Neish (*loc. cit.*). Apparently without further investigation the reagent was pronounced unsatisfactory and rejected in favour of *m*-nitrobenzoic acid, a rather expensive reagent. The following procedure adopted by us has yielded results which compare favourably with any known method.

TABLE III

ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths R ₂ O ₃ added.	ThO ₂ obtained.
0.1180 g.	—	0.1186 g. 0.1186
0.1180	1.1450 g.	0.1182 0.1179
{ Monazite } 0.0900 }	0.4708	0.0904 0.0907

To the thorium solution, if strongly acid, dilute ammonia is added dropwise until the solution reacts but faintly acid to *methyl red*. It is then diluted to 100 c.c. and heated to boiling. Hot 1% benzoic acid solution (100 c.c.) is added with vigorous stirring followed by 5% ammonium acetate until the liquid reacts at this stage just neutral. A precipitate results which settles quickly. This is filtered through Whatman No. 41. After washing with hot 0.25% benzoic acid the precipitate is returned to the original beaker and dissolved in hot dilute nitric acid and precipitation is repeated. The second precipitate after complete washing is ignited and weighed as the dioxide. The results are shown in the following table.

TABLE IV

ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths added.	ThO ₂ obtained.
0.1140 g.	—	{ 0.1142 g. 0.1141
0.1140	0.4580 g.	{ 0.1141 0.1142
0.1140	0.5712	{ 0.1145 0.1148
0.1140	1.1424	{ 0.1148 0.1146
{ Monazite } 0.0900 }	0.4708	{ 0.0900 0.0904

Ammonium Benzoate.—This reagent has not been referred to previously.

The nearly neutral solution is diluted to 200 c.c., acidified with 2 c.c. of glacial acetic acid and cold 3% ammonium benzoate is run in a thin stream with constant stirring until about 100 c.c. have been added for every 0.1 g. of thorium dioxide supposed to be present. The precipitate is now left on a water-bath and after it has settled (usually 30 minutes) as much of the supernatant liquid as possible is poured through a Whatman No. 41 filter, without disturbing the precipitate. It is now stirred up with hot 0.5% benzoic acid, filtered, and washed with the same reagent. The washed precipitate is transferred back to the original beaker and dissolved in a minimum of dilute hydrochloric acid. The solution is diluted to 150 c.c. and dilute ammonia is

run down from a burette until slight turbidity results. Precipitation is completed by adding a slight excess of ammonium benzoate reagent. The precipitate is next filtered, washed with hot 0.5% benzoic acid, and ignited to the oxide. The following table shows the results obtained.

TABLE V

ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths R ₂ O ₃ added.	ThO ₄ *obtained.
0.1140 g.	—	0.1142 g. 0.1141
0.1140	0.4580 g.	0.1141
0.1140	0.5712	0.1145 0.1148
0.1140	1.1424	0.1148 0.1146
{ Monazite 0.0900 }	0.4708	0.0900 0.0904
{ 0.0900 }	0.4708	0.0897 0.0900

Tannic Acid.— This reagent which has found such extensive use in the separation of columbium and tantalum does not seem to have attracted attention in this field. Neish (*loc. cit.*) refers to it only passingly.

The neutral solution is diluted to 200 c.c. after addition of 10 g. to 15 g. of ammonium chloride. Dilute acetic acid is then added dropwise until a drop of the solution just turns Congo red paper blue. Mineral acids should not be used for this acidification. The solution is heated just to boiling (it should not actually boil), and hot 5% tannic acid solution at the rate of 100 c.c. per 0.1 g. of thorium oxide is added slowly with constant stirring. The precipitate is left on a water-bath for 2 hours after which it is filtered through Whatman No 41 and washed with 2% tannic acid solution to which a

TABLE VI

ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths added.	ThO ₂ obtd.	ThO ₂ taken.	Cerite earths added.	ThO ₂ obtd.
0.0570 g.	—	0.0572 g.	0.1140 g.	1.1424 g.	0.1143 g.
0.0570	0.4580 g.	0.0573	0.1140	1.1424	0.1140
0.0570	0.4580	0.0574	0.1180	—	0.1183
0.1140	—	0.1139	0.1180	0.1401	0.1183
0.1140	0.4580	0.1142			
0.1140	0.5712	0.1148	{ Monazite 0.0900 }	0.4708	0.0897 0.0900

little ammonium nitrate or chloride has been added. The precipitate with the filtered paper is transferred to the original beaker and boiled with about 40 c.c. of dilute HCl (1:2) to dissolve the precipitate. Nitric acid should not be used. After thorough digestion dilute ammonia is added until the liquid reacts just neutral to Congo red. Precipitation and washing are repeated and the washed precipitate is ignited to the oxide. The results are given in Table VI.

In all cases, however, zirconium and quadrivalent cerium, if present, are simultaneously precipitated, a disadvantage that is shared by many reagents for thorium. It is thus necessary that cerium is reduced to the trivalent stage and zirconium is removed earlier by a simple precipitation with oxalic acid.

ANDHRA UNIVERSITY
WALTAIR.

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